

The dual effects of ethical leadership and culture on corporate governance: An empirical study

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ABSTRACT

Corporate governance is a cornerstone of organizational integrity, fostering transparency, accountability, and long-term sustainability. This study examines the dual influence of ethical leadership and organizational ethical culture on governance practices. Grounded in ethical leadership theory and organizational culture literature, the research conceptualizes ethical leadership as a behavioral catalyst and ethical culture as a systemic force that sustains governance implementation. A survey of 262 respondents across five countries, the study employed exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and structural equation modeling (SEM) to validate constructs and test hypotheses. Results of descriptive statistics indicated all measurements had acceptable construct validity and internal consistency. Results showed a significant positive Pearson correlation coefficient between ethical leadership and ethical culture. Regression analysis demonstrated that ethical culture was a stronger predictor of corporate governance than ethical leadership. Findings highlight the necessity of integrating ethical leadership development with the institutionalization of ethical culture to enhance governance effectiveness. The study contributes to the growing literature on corporate governance within ESG by offering empirical evidence and practical guidance for organizations.

Keywords: ethical leadership, ethical culture, corporate governance, ESG

1. Introduction

Corporate governance refers to the system of rules, practices, and processes by which a company is directed and controlled. Its main goal is to ensure responsible and ethical management, focusing on long-term value creation for all stakeholders (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2015). Key elements of effective governance include transparency, accountability, the role of the board, and compliance (Cadbury, 1992). Transparency builds trust and supports informed decision-making, while accountability enhances oversight and risk reduction (Solomon, 2020). Fairness protects stakeholder rights, and compliance ensures adherence to laws, regulations, and ethical standards (International Finance Corporation [IFC], 2018).

Research shows that companies with strong governance frameworks tend to perform better financially and socially. For example, Aguilera, Williams, Conley and Rupp (2008) note that governance systems prioritizing stakeholder engagement help firms manage challenges like technological change and shifting consumer demands. These systems also help balance short-term profit with long-term sustainability (Porter & Kramer, 2011).

From a stakeholder perspective, companies with diverse boards report a 15% higher return on equity (Deloitte, 2020), while those with high governance scores achieve 25% greater total shareholder returns over five years (McKinsey & Company, 2020). Strong governance supports ethical practices, builds trust with investors and employees, and enhances customer confidence (Tricker, 2019). In fact, 66% of consumers globally are willing to

pay more for ethically and sustainably operated brands (Nielsen, 2023).

Internally, governance acts as a safeguard against unethical practices like fraud and corruption. La Porta et al. (1999) suggest that clear rules and accountability in governance discourage misconduct. In contrast, executive misbehavior and poor ethics can weaken governance systems (Eccles, Ioannou, & Serafeim, 2020). Companies with strong governance structures are 40% less likely to face major governance failures (Harvard Law School Forum on Corporate Governance, 2021), highlighting the importance of board oversight and transparency (Gregory & Ninian, 2023). Today, governance also protects societal interests, especially as regulation and public scrutiny increase.

Modern businesses face growing pressure to address environmental, social, and governance (ESG) challenges. To meet these demands, companies must balance profitability with social and environmental responsibilities. A recent PWC (2023) survey found that 86% of global investors expect greater corporate disclosure on environmental and social issues. While governance focuses on structure and compliance, it does not fully explain how ethical leadership and ethical culture contribute to strong governance outcomes. Although strong governance deters unethical behavior and supports responsible practices, the role of ethical leadership—leaders promoting ethical conduct—and ethical culture—shared organizational values—requires more study. For instance, while diverse boards and high governance ratings correlate with better financial results and fewer failures, it is unclear how much ethical leadership influences these outcomes, or how culture reinforces governance and stakeholder trust.

Despite growing interest in organizational ethics and governance, a clear research gap remains in understanding how governance, ethical leadership, and ethical culture collectively influence risk reduction, sustainability, and stakeholder satisfaction. To address this gap, the present study investigates the role of ethical leadership and ethical culture in shaping governance effectiveness. Specifically, the study aims to: (1) examine the relationships among ethical leadership, ethical culture, and governance performance; and (2) assess how these relationships may differ across various cultural and institutional contexts. By pursuing these objectives, the research seeks to offer practical insights for organizations and policymakers aiming to enhance governance implementation. Furthermore, the study highlights the critical role of ethical leadership and culture in fostering long-term organizational success, sustainability, and positive societal impact.

2. Literature review

2.1 Corporate Governance

Corporate governance is grounded in core principles such as accountability, transparency, fairness, and responsibility, and plays a vital role in promoting ethical and effective corporate management (OECD, 2015). Its importance has intensified following major corporate scandals in the U.S. during the 1990s and the East Asian financial crisis of 1997, which exposed significant weaknesses in governance systems (Claessens, Djankov & Lang, 2000). Corporate governance not only involves formal rules and procedures but also supports ethical and efficient management practices aimed at achieving long-term business objectives. Reforms have increasingly focused on embedding ethical values into corporate systems to ensure sustainable governance and stakeholder trust (Kaptein, 2008).

To evaluate governance effectiveness, several tools have been developed. These include governance ratings from ISS, MSCI, and Sustainalytics, which assess risk areas such as board structure, shareholder rights, and corporate disclosure (ISS, 2023; MSCI, 2023; Sustainalytics, 2023). Governance indices like the FTSE Good Governance Index and the S&P Governance Index highlight firms with superior governance practices (Bassen, Meyer & Schlange, 2006). Other assessment methods include stakeholder surveys, in-depth case studies (Gompers, Ishii & Metrick, 2003), and financial indicators like return on equity and return on assets (Bhagat & Bolton, 2008). These tools are expected to be reliable, valid, relevant, and comparable (Kaptein, 2011). However, these tools are predominantly external and market-based orientation, which does not sufficiently capture the internal governance dynamics within an organization. Most of them are designed for cross-company comparisons in investment or regulatory contexts, focusing primarily on publicly available data and high-level indicators. In contrast, this study examined corporate's governance effectiveness from an internal management perspective. Therefore, we adopted BICG's Corporate Governance Assessment Tool, which offers a more detailed and context-specific evaluation of internal governance practices with 58 indicators across five dimensions: shareholder rights, board responsibilities, transparency, internal controls, and stakeholder engagement (Baltic Institute of Corporate Governance, 2021). This tool assesses corporate governance from internal employees' perspectives which is applicable to objective of this study.

Several factors influence corporate governance effectiveness, such as company size, ownership structures, legal systems, and national culture (Aguilera et al., 2008; Clarke, 2007). Internal drivers including ethical leadership, board independence, and management competence are also critical (Daily, Dalton & Cannella, 2003). Considering growing stakeholder expectations, increased media scrutiny, and pressures from globalization have further emphasized the need for robust and ethically grounded governance practices. Ethical leadership fosters integrity, accountability, and responsible decision-making at all levels, while a strong ethical culture reinforces

norms and values that support governance compliance and ethical conduct (Treviño & Nelson, 2016). Together, they serve as foundational elements that influence governance quality, making them especially relevant for internal governance assessments. Therefore, ethical leadership and ethical culture were selected as key variables in this study because two factors shape how governance principles are interpreted and practiced within corporates.

2.2 Ethical Leadership

Burns (1978) introduced ethical leadership as a way for leaders to promote shared moral values and inspire ethical behavior. Brown, Treviño and Harrison (2005) mention how leaders shape ethical behavior through role modeling, fairness, and accountability. Supports the idea that ethical leadership influences employee conduct and governance quality. Ethical leaders model fairness and integrity and reward ethical behavior while discouraging misconduct (Mayer et al., 2009; Neubert et al., 2013).

There are various tools to measure ethical leadership. These tools assess a leader's traits like integrity, decision-making, and ethical influence (Treviño, Hartman & Brown, 2000; Kaptein, 2011). The Ethical Leadership Scale (ELS) developed by Brown et al. (2005) is widely used and focuses on role modeling and accountability. The Ethical Leadership at Work Questionnaire adds elements like power-sharing and concern for sustainability (Kalshoven et al., 2011). The Servant Leadership Scale includes ethical aspects but focuses on empowerment and emotional support (Liden et al., 2008). Yukl, Mahsud, Hassan and Prussia (2013) introduced a multidimensional approach, but its core elements—like honesty and fairness—are already in the ELS. Based on Kaptein's (2017) suggestion, validity, reliability, and adaptability are important when choosing which tool to use. This study used ELS for assessing ethical leadership, due to its simplicity and strong foundation.

Prior research suggests that ethical leadership enhances organizational governance by fostering trust, enforcing ethical standards, and shaping a culture of integrity. Leaders who demonstrate ethical behavior set a tone that promotes fairness, transparency, and accountability across the organization (Brown & Treviño, 2006; Eisenbeiss, 2012). Ethical leaders not only strengthen the effectiveness of governance systems but also guide policy development and support regulatory compliance (Mayer et al., 2012).

2.3 Corporate Ethical Culture

Corporate ethical culture refers to the shared values and norms that guide ethical behavior within an organization (Treviño, Butterfield, & McCabe, 1998). It affects how employees respond to ethical challenges and is linked to responsibilities like social responsibility and environmental care (Schein, 2010).

Several ethical theories support ethical culture. Utilitarianism focuses on maximizing benefits for stakeholders (Mill, 1863). Deontological ethics, based on Kant, emphasizes rules and duties (Kant, 1785). Virtue ethics promotes personal traits like honesty and integrity (MacIntyre, 1981).

Researchers have developed many tools to measure ethical culture, such as:

- Ethical Climate Questionnaire (ECQ) – Proposed by Victor and Cullen (1988), this tool measures ethical climate across nine dimensions related to three ethical criteria (egoism, benevolence, and principle). It consists of 36 items.
- Corporate Ethical Values Scale (CEVS) – Developed by Hunt, Wood & Chonko (1989), this scale assesses how employees perceive ethical values within their organization. Generally, uses a 5-item scale to evaluate the alignment of organizational values with employees' ethical perceptions (Hunt, Wood, & Chonko, 1989). It measures the ethical values endorsed by the organization and the perceived ethical behaviors promoted by management.
- Multidimensional Ethics Scale (MES) – Created by Reidenbach & Robin (1990), this tool evaluates ethical judgments across different scenarios, offering a broad perspective on ethical decision-making. Varies based on the number of scenarios presented, typically involving multiple items per scenario to assess different ethical dimensions (Reidenbach & Robin, 1990).
- The Corporate Ethical Virtues Model Scale (CEVMS), developed by Kaptein (2008), is a questionnaire designed to assess ethical culture within organizations. The scale consists of 58 items distributed across eight dimensions: clarity, congruence of supervisors, congruence of senior management, feasibility, supportability, transparency, discussability, and sanctionability.
- The Corporate Ethical Virtues (CEV-32) scale, developed by DeBode, Armenakis, Field, and Walker (2013), is a condensed version of the original 58-item CEV scale conceptualized by Kaptein (2008). The CEV-32 was designed to reduce respondent burden and enhance the scale's practicality and usability for researchers.
- Corporate Integrity Capacity Measure (CICM), proposed by Simha & Cullen (2012), assesses an organization's ability to maintain ethical standards, focusing on integrity mechanisms.

A strong ethical culture supports good governance by promoting transparency, accountability, and ethical choices (Kaptein, 2011; Schein, 2010). It reduces misconduct, boosts trust and helps implement whistleblower systems and fair practices (Ferrell et al., 2019). Ethical culture also improves performance, employee motivation, and innovation (Treviño, Weaver & Reynolds, 1998; Schwartz, 2013; Weaver, Treviño, & Cochran, 1999).

Beyond internal benefits, ethical culture enhances reputation, attracts investors, and reduces legal and compliance risks (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Paine, 1994). It ensures consistency between values and actions and promotes long-term focus (Hosmer, 1995; Treviño & Nelson, 2021). Ethical organizations foster trust, manage

risks, and build resilience (Bazerman & Tenbrunsel, 2011).

3. Research Method

3.1 Hypotheses development

According to social learning theory by Bandura (1977), employees learn ethical behavior by observing and imitating ethical leaders. Supports the idea that ethical leadership can shape organizational culture and influence governance. This idea helps explain how ethical leadership and ethical culture work together. When leaders act ethically, they set an example for employees to follow (Brown & Treviño, 2006). Their behavior supports ethical standards and encourages staff to follow the company's code of conduct. Ethical leaders help shape a culture that supports doing the right thing (Kristijono et al., 2022). At the same time, a strong ethical culture makes ethical leadership more effective by reinforcing positive behavior (Treviño, Butterfield & McCabe, 2003). This shows a two-way relationship, ethical leadership supports ethical culture, and ethical culture strengthens leadership. Therefore, this study hypothesized:

H1: There is a positive relationship between ethical leadership and ethical culture.

Ethical leadership also improves corporate governance. Leaders who act ethically promote accountability and openness, which strengthens the organization's rules and oversight systems (Mayer, Kuenzi, Greenbaum, Bardes & Salvador, 2009). These leaders create a workplace that supports integrity and fairness (Eisenbeiss, 2012). Research shows that ethical leadership leads to better governance by encouraging honest decision-making and responsible behavior (Mayer, Aquino, Greenbaum & Kuenzi, 2012). Ethical leaders help build trust, which is key to effective governance. Therefore, this study hypothesized:

H2: Ethical leadership has a positive influence on corporate governance.

According to stakeholder theory, companies should consider the needs of all stakeholders—not just shareholders, but also supports the role of ethical culture and governance in promoting fairness, trust, and accountability across all stakeholder relationships (Freeman, 2001). A strong ethical culture helps organizations act in line with shared values. Kaptein (2011) found that ethical culture improves risk management and helps companies meet legal and ethical standards, especially when they are closely monitored by regulators. This supports good governance and reduces the risk of wrongdoing. Therefore, this study hypothesized:

H3: Ethical culture has a positive influence on corporate governance.

Based on the relationship among three variables, the research framework is depicted as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research framework

3.2 Instrumentation

To assess corporate governance practices, the study employed the BICG Corporate Governance Assessment Tool developed by the Baltic Institute of Corporate Governance (2021). This tool includes 58 indicators grouped into five categories: shareholder protection and rights, board of directors, transparency and reporting, control environment, and stakeholders (B). It is specifically designed to evaluate alignment with international corporate governance standards and best practices.

Ethical leadership was measured using the Ethical Leadership Scale (ELS) developed by Brown et al. (2005). The ELS consists of 10 items capturing core dimensions of ethical leadership, such as integrity, fairness, accountability, and role modeling. This scale is recognized for its robust psychometric properties, generalizability, and practical relevance across organizational settings. It was selected over alternative tools due to its conciseness, reliability, and strong empirical validation.

This study employed the 32-item Corporate Ethical Virtues Scale (CEV-32), which retains the original eight dimensions from the full CEV-58: clarity, congruence of supervisors, congruence of management, feasibility, supportability, transparency, discussability, and sanctionability, with four items representing each dimension. CEV-32 was chosen for its balance between comprehensive coverage and respondent manageability, offering strong reliability while minimizing the risk of survey fatigue.

3.3 Data collection

The questionnaire contains two main sections: demographic information and measurements of variables, including ethical leadership, ethical culture, and corporate governance performance. Part I collects demographic information about respondents, such as age, gender, education level, job position, and job experience. This information provides a profile of the sample and enables analyses of differences among respondent subgroups. In Part II, each variable is assessed using measurements adapted from well-established English scales drawn from previous research as mentioned above.

This study gathered data from five countries: Indonesia, Mongolia, and Taiwan in Asia, and Somalia and Mozambique in Africa. The English measurements were translated into the native languages of the target countries, with minor semantic adjustments made to certain items. Each version of the questionnaire was back-translated into English to ensure measurement consistency. Five questionnaire versions were developed, including Mandarin Chinese, English, Indonesian, Mongolian, and Somali.

Participants rate their agreement with each statement using a scale with 5 levels, ranging from “Strongly Disagree”, “Disagree”, “Natural”, “Agree”, to “Strongly Agree”. The choice of scale length can affect the sensitivity and reliability of the data, with 5-point scales being the most common due to their balance of simplicity and informational depth (Joshi, Kale, Chandel & Pal, 2015).

A convenience sampling approach, namely choosing respondents who were easy to reach, was used to collect samples through five links of different languages of online questionnaires. Respondents working in private sectors were invited to participate in this survey. Before any data collection can occur, informed permission was acquired. This research ensures every participant’s involvement was entirely voluntary, and responders are assured of confidentiality and anonymity.

4. Results

4.1 Profile of samples

A total of 359 individuals from five countries participated in the survey, from which 262 valid responses were obtained. Most valid responses originated from Taiwan (44%), followed by Mongolia (21%), Indonesia (17%), and the remaining 18% from two African countries.

Participants ranged in age from 18 to over 65 years, with the largest proportion (42%) falling within the 25–34 age group. Among the valid responses, 49% identified as male and 51% as female. Regarding educational attainment, a majority (52%) had completed at least a college degree; specifically, 26% held a bachelor’s degree, 13% a high school diploma, and 9% reported other qualifications. Respondents were employed across a range of occupational sectors, with the highest representation from professionals and technicians (39%), followed by the service sector (21%), production (19%), management and administration (8%), finance and business (4%), healthcare (2%), and other sectors (7%). In terms of job level, 46% were entry-level employees, 19% were mid-level managers, 14% were senior managers, 10% held executive or top management positions, and 11% reported other roles. Collectively, these demographic characteristics offer a profile of the samples.

4.2. Validity and reliability tests of measurements

To ensure the quality of measurement in this study, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to assess construct validity, and internal consistency reliability was evaluated using Cronbach’s alpha. For the ethical leadership construct, Principal Component Analysis with Varimax rotation was employed to identify the underlying factor structure. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.799, indicating that the sample was suitable for factor analysis. Additionally, Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 428.48$, $df = 21$, $p < 0.001$), confirming the appropriateness of the data for factor extraction. Three items were removed due to cross-loading, and the remaining items exhibited factor loadings above 0.5, suggesting strong associations with their respective factors. The rotated component matrix revealed two factors with eigenvalues greater than 1, collectively accounting for 59.95% of the total variance. The reliability of the ethical leadership scale was supported by a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.77, indicating acceptable internal consistency. The mean item scores for ethical leadership ranged from 3.66 to 4.26, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of ethical leadership

Item	Mean	S.D.	Factor Loading		Cronbach’s α
			1	2	
EL_3	3.77	0.961	0.727		0.77
EL_4	3.79	0.815	0.720		
EL_7	3.84	0.895	0.762		

EL_9	3.66	0.949	0.792
EL_5	4.06	0.683	0.754
EL_8	4.10	0.722	0.750
EL_10	4.26	0.657	0.792

To examine the construct of ethical culture, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation was conducted to identify the underlying factor structure. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.723, indicating that the dataset was suitable for factor analysis. Furthermore, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 913.76$, $df = 66$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that the correlations among variables were sufficiently large for factor extraction. A total of 12 items were removed due to cross-loadings or low factor loadings. The remaining items all demonstrated factor loadings above 0.50, indicating strong alignment with their respective factors. The rotated component matrix revealed five distinct factors with eigenvalues exceeding 1, collectively explaining 66.29% of the total variance. Internal consistency for the ethical culture scale was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.68, which is considered acceptable. The mean scores of the ethical culture items ranged from 3.32 to 4.36, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of ethical culture

Item	Mean	S.D.	Factor Loading				Cronbach's α
			1	2	3	4	
EC_4	3.88	.849	.878				0.68
EC_5	3.88	.810	.854				
EC_6	3.87	.860	.816				
EC_2	4.36	.588		.805			
EC_1	4.25	.617		.804			
EC_3	4.17	.651		.740			
EC_17	3.51	.870			.812		
EC_18	3.38	.934			.776		
EC_16	3.56	.804			.675		
EC_11	3.32	1.170				.855	
EC_10	3.50	1.134				.716	
EC_12	3.34	1.037				.575	

To examine the construct of corporate governance, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Varimax rotation was conducted to identify the underlying factor structure. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.938, indicating excellent suitability of the sample for factor analysis. Additionally, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 1883.63$, $df = 91$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that the data were appropriate for factor extraction. A total of six items were removed due to cross-loading or low factor loadings. The remaining items all demonstrated loadings above 0.50, suggesting strong associations with their respective factors. The rotated component matrix revealed five distinct factors with eigenvalues greater than 1, which together accounted for 58.51% of the total variance. Internal consistency of the corporate governance scale was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, yielding a value of 0.92, indicating excellent reliability. The mean scores of the corporate governance items ranged from 3.42 to 3.98, as reported in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of corporate governance

Item	Mean	S.D.	Factor Loading		Cronbach's α
			1	2	
CG_11	3.63	.818	.738		0.92
CG_5	3.71	.812	.732		
CG_10	3.75	.814	.728		
CG_8	3.84	.804	.712		
CG_7	3.74	.885	.700		
CG_1	3.59	.887	.683		
CG_9	3.42	.918	.682		
CG_2	3.71	.885	.667		
CG_3	3.78	.832	.647		
CG_12	3.53	1.060	.537		
CG_13	3.87	.943		.884	
CG_14	3.91	.795		.710	
CG_15	3.70	.957		.768	
CG_16	3.98	.830		.539	

4.3 Hypotheses test

A structural equation modeling (SEM) approach was employed to test the proposed hypotheses. Results from the structural model indicated a good overall fit between the data and the model: $\chi^2(8) = 11.20$, CMIN/DF = 1.026, GFI = 0.910, AGFI = 0.883, TLI = 0.996, CFI = 0.997, and RMSEA = 0.01. All fit indices met the commonly accepted thresholds recommended in prior research (Hu & Bentler, 1999; McNeish & Wolf, 2023). The correlation analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between ethical leadership and ethical culture, with a Pearson's correlation coefficient of ($r = 0.631, p < .001$), thus supporting Hypothesis H1. The path analysis further indicated that ethical leadership had a direct and significant positive effect on corporate governance ($\beta = 0.356, p < .001$), supporting Hypothesis H2. Additionally, ethical culture exhibited a strong direct positive effect on corporate governance ($\beta = 0.78, p < .001$), supporting Hypothesis H3. The R-squared value for corporate governance indicated that 74% of its variance was explained by the combined effects of ethical leadership and ethical culture, demonstrating higher explanatory power of the model. These results suggest that ethical leadership and ethical culture interact mutually, and both exert significantly positive influences on corporate governance practices, as illustrated in Figure 2.

*** p < .001

Figure 2: Results of hypotheses

To further examine the potential interaction effect, a multiple regression analysis was conducted with ethical leadership, ethical culture, and their interaction term as predictors of corporate governance. The overall model was statistically significant, $F(3, 258) = 56.598$, $p < .001$, with an R^2 of 0.397, indicating that approximately 39.7% of the variance in corporate governance was explained by the predictors. However, the interaction between ethical leadership and ethical culture was not statistically significant ($\beta = -0.228$, $p = .702$), suggesting no meaningful interaction effect.

These results indicated that a simpler model including only the main effects of ethical leadership and ethical culture may be more appropriate for explaining corporate governance. Therefore, the SEM approach remains the preferred analytical method in this study. Although the interaction effect between the two predictors was not supported empirically, both still demonstrated overall contributions to corporate governance.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The results of this study provide empirical support for the dual influence of ethical leadership and ethical culture on corporate governance. Consistent with prior research, a moderate positive correlation was identified between ethical leadership and ethical culture ($r = 0.631^*$), indicating a mutually reinforcing relationship. Notably, ethical culture exerted a stronger effect on corporate governance ($\beta = 0.78^{***}$), highlighting the critical role of organizational ethical standards in sustaining effective governance practices (Ruiz et al., 2014). While ethical leadership demonstrated a comparatively smaller impact ($\beta = 0.356^{***}$), it still significantly contributed to governance outcomes by shaping ethical behavior and reinforcing accountability within leadership roles (Neubaum et al., 2019; Brown et al., 2005).

These findings collectively emphasize the importance of both ethical leadership and ethical culture as complementary drivers of robust corporate governance (Kaptein, 2008; Treviño et al., 1998). This study advances theoretical understanding in the domains of corporate governance and organizational ethics by empirically validating the dual influence of ethical leadership and ethical culture. The findings support and extend existing ethical and governance theories by illustrating how leadership behavior and organizational culture interact to shape governance outcomes. The moderate correlation between ethical leadership and ethical culture suggests a reciprocal dynamic that warrants further theoretical exploration. Moreover, the stronger impact of ethical culture underscores its foundational role in sustaining governance quality, aligning with the view that ethical norms embedded in organizational systems can exert more pervasive and long-lasting effects than individual leadership alone. These findings contribute to the broader discourse on ethical infrastructure by demonstrating that while ethical leaders initiate ethical practices, it is the deeply rooted culture that ensures consistency and sustainability in governance. This resonates with institutional theory, which posits that durable systems and norms are essential for the long-term legitimacy and performance of organizations.

For practitioners, the results offer actionable insights into strengthening ethical governance within organizations. The significant role of ethical culture suggests that institutionalizing shared ethical values, norms, and systems should be a strategic priority for boards and top management. This may include revising codes of conduct, embedding ethics into performance evaluations, and ensuring alignment between stated values and organizational practices. Although ethical leadership had a comparatively smaller effect, its meaningful influence highlights the need to recruit, train, and support leaders who model ethical behavior. Organizations should invest in ethical leadership development programs and cultivate environments that promote transparency, accountability, and value-based decision-making. A dual strategy that synchronizes individual leadership development with systemic cultural initiatives can generate a synergistic effect, amplifying the overall impact on governance outcomes.

Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on corporate governance by empirically demonstrating the mutually reinforcing relationship between ethical leadership and ethical culture. While ethical leadership serves as a visible expression of organizational values, ethical culture embeds those values into daily operations, decision-making processes, and stakeholder relationships. Ethical culture emerged as the stronger predictor of governance quality, but the influence of leadership behavior remains essential in reinforcing and modeling ethical standards. This research affirms that effective governance cannot depend solely on individual actors—it must be embedded within the organization's cultural fabric. The findings offer both theoretical clarity and practical guidance for corporate leaders and policymakers seeking to enhance ESG alignment, ethical accountability, and long-term performance through integrated ethical governance frameworks.

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